

Paper on wave exposure index

Deliverable 2.2

Paper on wave exposure index

Deliverable 2.2

How to Cite

Burrows, M.T., Heikes-Knapton, S., Addamo, A.M., Costello M.J. 2023. Paper on wave exposure index. Nord University, *MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 2.2*, 22 pp.

Version: V1.0

Data of release: 31st August 2023

Instrument call: HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-12

Start of the project: 1st January 2023

Duration of the project: 40 months

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

MPA Europe is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (Grant Agreement: 101059988). UK participants in Horizon Europe Project MPA Europe are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10067934 JNCC and 10069750 SAMS.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect that of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.2 overview

This present document a Europe-wide, continental-scale, high resolution (100m) gridded coastal dataset on summed wave fetch (the distance to the nearest land around locations of interest), fetch orientation (the weighted mean angle of fetch vectors) and fetch directionality (the weighted standard deviation of fetch orientation). The resulting availability of this important ecological predictor should develop understanding of biodiversity in coastal areas and help better place future marine protected areas to maximise their effectiveness. The information provided is crucial for policy-relevant research focusing on MPA designation, in particular, mapping biodiversity patterns, and will feed the main subsequent task of Prioritisation (WP5) of systematic conservation planning to design (prioritise locations for an) MPA networks.

A Europe-wide high-resolution model of coastal wave fetch

Abstract

Shallow coastal marine habitats are strongly influenced by waves. In this study, we present a Europe-wide, continental-scale, high resolution (100m) gridded coastal dataset on summed wave fetch (the distance to the nearest land around locations of interest), fetch orientation (the weighted mean angle of fetch vectors) and fetch directionality (the weighted standard deviation of fetch orientation). Three different search patterns to check for land were explored: a regular 3-zone search with decreasing intervals between land check locations at greater distance, and random distance with random angle searches. Random distances were drawn from log or square root of maximum search distance (200km), back-transformed to give actual search distances. Adding randomness overcame some of the biases of the regular 3-zone search pattern and doing this with the regular 3-zone search proved computationally faster than the random angle/random distance methods. Scaling this method to continents and ultimately globally was achieved by producing tiled landmass grids at two scales: locally for wave fetch computation (100m scale for 5 x 5 or 2 x 2° latitude/longitude tiles) and on larger scales (5km scale for Europe, or 5 x 5° latitude/longitude tiles for global fetch evaluation). Longitudinal resolution of these grids in degrees was set to the desired size using the width of a 1° grid cell at the mid latitude of the cell. Where land check locations exceeded the bounds of the smaller tiles, searches for land reverted to the larger background tiles. Landmass data was derived from the freely available OpenStreetMap source.

Summed fetch proved highly effective at predicting the composition of rocky shore communities in a test dataset of recent surveys in Scotland. High values of summed wave fetch were associated with communities dominated by species typical of exposed shores (coralline algae) and low values with communities dominated by large brown seaweeds (*Ascophyllum nodosum*, *Fucus vesiculosus*, *Fucus spiralis*). Effects of fetch on communities were modified by shore extent such that more extensive shores had a greater mix of wave-affinity species than less extensive ones. Fetch orientation did not predict any additional variation in community structure. The resulting availability of this important ecological predictor should develop understanding of biodiversity in coastal areas and help better place future marine protected areas to maximise their effectiveness.

Introduction

Wave exposure has long been known to have a profound influence on the composition of ecological communities on rocky shorelines (Ballantine, 1961; Lewis, 1964; Ricketts and Calvin, 1992).

Describing shore environments as wave-exposed or wave-sheltered is at the core of most experimental studies of the ecology and behaviour of rocky shore organisms, from feeding rates of predators (Menge, 1978), foraging behaviour and use of shelters (Burrows and Hughes, 1989), morphological characteristics of furoid macroalgae (Ruuskanen et al., 1999) and gastropods (Crothers, 1983), and even variation in chromosome numbers between exposed and sheltered shore populations of the same species (Page, 1988; Pascoe, 2006).

The need for quantitative metrics of wave exposure has largely been met through measures based on coastal openness (Baardseth, 1970), based on the number of angular sectors with fetch >7.5km) or wave fetch, the summed distance to the nearest land in angular sectors, either 16 22.5° sectors (Burrows et al., 2008; Isaeus, 2004; Thomas, 1986) or 32 11.25° sectors (Burrows, 2012). The approach has been developed by multiple authors (gridded search by Finlayson in (Chollett and Mumby, 2012), detecting land by projecting radiating lines for point locations (Ekebom et al., 2003) (Davies et al., 2007; Yesson et al., 2015) using line crossing methods. Most of these methods developed from needing to progress from qualitative to quantitative measures of wave exposure to better understand the ecological effects of wave action without the absolute necessity for measuring

wave forces. Baardseth (1970) used his index to estimate quantities of seaweeds across whole coastlines, as did (Yesson et al., 2015) in estimating extents of potential seaweed habitats. Including wave fetch estimates among larger sets of environmental conditions allows estimation of beta diversity in coral reefs (Harborne et al., 2006). Beyond ecological studies, wave fetch mapping has been used in assessing the susceptibility of coastlines to erosion (Fitton et al., 2016) and the potential coastal protection offered by coastal vegetation such as saltmarshes (Gilbertson et al., 2020). Fetch values have been combined with wind velocity information to create wave exposure indices, usually the average windspeed and incidence in each angular sector, on the expectation that waves would increase with the square of the windspeed. Yet including wind information does not appear to give greater predictive power (Burrows et al., 2008; Isaeus, 2004), fortunately for prediction purposes given the lack of wind observations at necessary scales. In the absence of more complex physical models, wave fetch alone may serve as a useful proxy for wave exposure. The aims of this study were to develop methods for extensive, continental- and global-scale mapping of measures of coastal wave exposure based on wave fetch, and to validate the predictive abilities of these metrics using known dependencies of composition of rocky shore communities on wave exposure. By production of such methods and maps, we aim to facilitate the generation of predictive maps of biodiversity in coastal regions to feed into the process of selecting effective sets of marine protected areas at continental scales.

Methods

As in Burrows (2008) and (2012), estimation of coastal wave fetch in this study used an iterative search for the nearest land mass around each focal cell. The process involved digitizing high-resolution polygons of landmasses at low resolution over larger scales, typically 5km over 1000s of km, and at high resolution (20-100m) over smaller scales (10s–100s km) to create tiled maps of wave exposure. Search patterns for the nearest land in 32 11.5° angular sectors used either regularly spaced checks over three search domains (distant, middle and local) or a randomized distance and angle. The maximum distance for land searches was usually 200km. All code was written as Rcpp functions (Eddelbuettel and Balamuta, 2018) in R (R Core Team, 2022) and is available at <https://github.com/michaelburrows/> (to be updated).

Coastal grids

Gridded landmasses were created from OpenStreetMap land polygons (land_polygons_split_3857.shp from <https://osmdata.openstreetmap.de/data/land-polygons.html>) using the rasterize function in R (Hijmans, 2022). Grids were assigned as 1 for land and zero for ocean at the desired resolution. The method adopted here used latitude-longitude grids but analyses using projected data (as in Burrows, 2012; Burrows et al., 2008) were possible for more spatially limited model domains. For the Europe-scale analysis presented here, high-resolution grids were created at 100m resolution over 5° latitude / longitude tiles with latitudinal grid cell dimensions as 0.1km/111.325km = 0.0008982708° and longitudinal dimensions as $\cos(\text{mid tile latitude}) \times 0.1\text{km}/111.325\text{km}$. This approach produced approximately 100m grids over tiles of dimensions of 556km North-South, and variable widths for East-West). A low-resolution grid of 5km grid cells (0.04491354° latitude by 0.02734163° longitude) was created for the whole of Europe, 15°W-45°E and 30°-75°N (4440km by 3850km), using the middle latitude (52.5°N) for cell size calculations. Wave fetch and orientation calculations were restricted to coastal regions, here all ocean cells <5km from land.

Search patterns

The search for land aimed to identify the influential landmasses as effectively and efficiently as possible. For the regular three-zone search, as in in Burrows (2012), distant land checks were made

every 100 cells (10km intervals) up to the maximum search distance (200km, Fig. 1a), middle-zone land checks made every 10 cells (1km intervals) up to 20km away from focal cell, and local land checks every cell (100m intervals) up to 10 cells distant (1km, Figure 1). Random jitter of up half the interval adopted for outer and middle zones was used to displace land check locations (Figure 1c,d) Search patterns with random distances and directions to check locations were trialled using random log10 distances and squared distances. For log10 searches, distances were back-transformed random numbers between the local search transition distance $\log_{10}(10)$ and the maximum search distance (maxdist), $\log_{10}(\text{maxdist})$; and for squared random distances searches, the square of a random number between the square root of the local search transition distance, $\sqrt{10}$, and $\sqrt{\text{maxdist}}$.

Wave fetch summed, wave fetch direction and angular standard deviation

Search algorithms produced fetch values as minimum distances, d_i , to the nearest land in each angular sector, q_i , around each focal grid cell, and summed to give total fetch, F . The mean angle of the fetch vectors, Φ , was calculated as the arctangent of summed products of the sine and cosine components of each fetch d_i and angle value q_i :

$$\Phi = \text{atan2} \left(\sum d_i \sin \theta_i, \sum d_i \cos \theta_i \right)$$

Angular standard deviation was also calculated as a measure of the overall directionality of wave fetch.

$$SD_{\phi} = \sqrt{\left(\sum \frac{d_i \sin \theta_i}{F} \right)^2 + \left(\sum \frac{d_i \cos \theta_i}{F} \right)^2}$$

Global-scale wave fetch estimation

The focus in this study has been on deriving wave fetch maps for Europe. On a global scale, the technique has also been used to produce local scale maps for any set of locations using the same two-scale tile methods. A five-degree latitude-longitude far-search map was digitized from the OpenStreetMap landmass dataset using the integer latitude-longitude location of the centre of the area of interest, and a 2-degree tile in the centre of the area for wave fetch estimation. Site specific wave fetch information could then be extracted from the modelled areas. The approach was trialled but not used for extraction of wave fetch values for comparison with algae productivity estimates in Pessarrodona et al. (2022).

Prediction tests

The effectiveness of the wave fetch algorithm as a predictor of ecological patterns was assessed using community data collected in summer from rocky seashores in Scotland in 2014-2015 and 2020-2022. The survey programme included repeated visits to 158 sites from the Solway Firth to the north of Shetland, including the Outer and Inner Hebrides and the entire mainland, over a wide range of wave exposures from Atlantic-facing open coastlines to sheltered sea lochs (fjords). Abundance estimates for around 60 species were collected during 60-minute surveys, extending over areas of 50m to 150m along the shore and from above the height of mean high water of spring tides to the lowest point of the tide during the survey. Surveys were always conducted within 120 minutes of the time of low water. Counts of organisms and measurements of percentage cover were made using 0.25m² quadrats (or smaller in the case of smaller organisms such as barnacles) placed haphazardly in the habitats known to have maximal abundance for those species. Species that were searched for but not found were recorded as absent ('Not seen'), while those for which the habitat was absent or inaccessible, such as kelps during higher states of tides or strong waves, were assigned as missing data ('Not recorded'). Numerical estimates of abundance were then classed into a 7-point scale

(SACFORN) using categories for specific groups of organisms. Full details of these abundance estimation methods are given in Burrows et al. (2008).

The centre of each survey area was recorded using handheld GPS (Garmin GPS76) or relocated on return visits using coordinates uploaded to mobile phone apps (Android Google Maps and QField). These locations were used to extract other site-specific environmental information using GIS and the extract function of the raster package. To reduce the effects of randomness in the land search algorithms, wave fetch was averaged over a 3 x 3 cell neighbourhood around the focal cell before extraction, reducing the resolution but improving the representation of local shoreline shape. Summed fetch was also averaged over a 21 x 21 cell, 2km neighbourhood to give a measure of context for the finer scale metrics. Fetch orientation (Φ above) was also averaged over a 3 x 3 neighbourhood by averaging sine and cosines of the fetch angle values and using the atan2 function to return an average orientation.

Principal components (PC) analysis of these data as category ranks, using 67 species with <10% missing data and with missing values assigned as zero, was used to produce PCs scores for each survey site. The first of these PCs (PC1) explained 15% of the variance and had high positive factor loadings for species that were associated with wave-exposed conditions (including the coralline alga, *Corallina officinalis*, and the exposed shore barnacle, *Chthamalus stellatus*) and negative factor loadings for those species associated with wave shelter (fucoid macroalgae: *Ascophyllum nodosum*, *Fucus vesiculosus* and *F. spiralis*, Supplementary Figure 1). PC1 scores for 254 surveys were related to summed wave fetch and other environmental predictors: average August sea surface temperatures (SST) (50km scale for 2002-2008 from Modis AQUA monthly composites), fetch orientation (Supplementary Figure 2) and shore extent, derived from an Ordnance Survey OpenData VectorMap product delineating the area between extreme high and low tides. Shore extent was taken as the total area of foreshore within 100m of the recorded central GPS location, obtained using a circular 100m radius buffer around each survey point. Shore extents ranged from <300m² to 35000m² and distinguished between narrow, steeply shelving shores with distinct vertical zonation and flatter, wider shores with a much longer distance from low to high tide marks. Summed wave fetch from earlier models of the same area (Burrows, 2012) was included for comparison. The predictive power of summed wave fetch from this and the earlier study, fetch orientation and the additional predictors of shore extent and summer temperatures was assessed by model fitting and selection using linear models (lm in R) compared using AIC (Burnham and Anderson, 2002).

Results

Patterns in summed wave fetch associated with different search methods

The regular three-zone search pattern produced some artifacts (Figure 4a). A sharp drop off in search intensity at the boundaries between the zones such that small land features became much less visible to the algorithm just beyond the transitions. The effect generated local repeating “shadows” of small islands and peninsulas as these features dropped in between the sampling intervals of the middle search zone (10 grid cells). Adding “jitter” to land check locations, a random shift of up to half the search interval in the x and y direction, removed the repeating artefacts completely (Figure 4b).

Using randomly derived angles and distances (Figure 2) for searches removed the further bias of the regular search pattern in searching for land at greater distances along diagonals (bishops move). Random distances were selected using back-transformed random log₁₀ values or random square root values up to the maximum search radius. The two options produced quite different outcomes, with random log₁₀ distances searching more sparsely in the distant zone (Figure 2c, d) and squared distances more sparsely in the middle zone (Figure 2a, b). This difference meant that log₁₀ searches

were less likely to be influenced by distant land than square root searches, but more likely to be influenced by nearby land. The frequency distribution of land check locations (Figure 3) clearly showed this difference, as well as the severe drop-off in search intensity beyond the middle zone for the regular 3-zone search.

Regular three-zone searches were considerably faster (37s for a 668 x 484 test set in Figure 4 with or without jitter) to run than random searches based on square root distances (48s) or log10 distances (68s). Regular searches with jitter were not obviously visibly different from random searches (Figure 4b vs Figure 4c and 4d) despite the sampling biases of the approach. Written in c++, the code ran fast enough to generate continental scale maps on multiple core processor machines in a few hours or less.

While the summed maps produced using the different search methods were similar, plots of differences in summed fetch values from the mean of all four methods showed their effectiveness at detecting landmasses at different distances (Figure 5). Random log10 distances produced lower values for summed wave fetch at distances up to 50km (5000 grid cells, Figure 5a) than the other methods: square-root distance or regular 3-zone searches (Figure 5b,c,d). Regular 3-zone searches without jitter produced more variable fetch sums than those with jitter (Figure 5d), as expected from the visible artifacts on the maps themselves.

Maps of wave fetch metrics

Application of the method effectively distinguishes between open coastal environments with likely greater wave exposure from places sheltered from ocean waves in enclosed, fjordic conditions (Figure 6a). Fetch orientation is directed towards the open ocean on exposed coastlines, and either across inlets or towards their openings in sheltered conditions (Figure 6b). Fetch angles are more omnidirectional in the middle of enclosed areas where standard deviation (SD) angle tends to zero (Figure 6c) and more unidirectional on open coastlines. Wind direction may be likely to have a greater influence on wave conditions where the dominant fetch comes from a particular direction.

Predictive power

Summed wave fetch was effective at predicting the first principal component of rocky shore community data from the surveys in Scotland (Figure 7, Table 1). Fetch previously estimated at 200m scale (Table 1 Model A vs Model D) explained a greater proportion of the variance than the novel 100m scale dataset. Averaging the 100-m scale data over a 2km area also produced a better fit (Table 1 Model H vs Model E).

Shore extent and summer sea surface temperature were significant covariates. For the 100m-scale wave fetch metric (Table 2 Model I), there was a significant interaction between shore extent and wave fetch such that, in wave exposure, more wave-sheltered species were found on more extensive shores (predicted PC1 decreased with shore extent) while, in wave shelter, more extensive shores tended to include more wave-exposed species. Using the older 200-m scale wave fetch sum (Table 2 Model B), the interaction effect was not evident: more extensive shores tended to be more dominated by large brown macroalgae irrespective of wave fetch (lower PC1 scores).

Lower PC1 scores (communities with less wave-exposed species) were associated with warmer August sea surface temperatures (Table 2) such that a 1°C increase in August SST was associated with a 0.8 (Model I) or 1.1 (Model B) reduction in PC1.

Adding fetch orientation to models (Table 1 Models J and K vs Models H and I) resulted in increased AIC values, suggesting that orientation itself had no further predictive value for this limited test dataset.

Discussion

The implementation of this faster computational approach to calculating maps of coastal wave fetch should prove useful in mapping and modelling. Direct physical models of wave climate can considerably improve predictive models for seagrass, for example (Bertelli et al., 2023). While such dynamic physical models are very useful and produce outputs that can be directly compared with field estimates (significant wave heights, wave spectra), they are rarely implemented at scales that allow prediction of habitat suitability or species distributions at national or international scales. Implementing spatially extensive models at finer scales, often to match with previously collected survey data, has been effective for estimating likely extents of kelp forests, for example (Bekkby and Moy, 2011; Burrows et al., 2018). The datasets from this study will be used to help model patterns of biodiversity across Europe's coastlines by fitting multiple predictive species distribution models to give patterns of biodiversity, useful for projecting effects of climate change on species distributions (Assis et al., 2018) or on changing patterns of species richness (García Molinos et al., 2016).

While regularised searches for land are simple and fast, they can result in artifacts that appear as repeating patterns on summed fetch maps when nearby features such as small islands or peninsulas "fall between the cracks" in the gridded search patterns. Such artifacts were detected and avoided here by the addition of random jitter to the regular search grid, a random displacement of the land check locations. Some bias due to the regular search grid remained, particularly in the detection of nearby land at greater distances along diagonals (45°, 135°, 215°, 305°) and the underrepresentation of distances just beyond search zone boundaries. Completely random searches for land based on random angles and random distances, skewed towards searches closer to the focal locations using log10 or square root transformations, removed the further geometrical biases of the regular search methods. All methods performed similarly well at distances beyond 5000 grid cells from the focal cell (50km). Random log10 distance searches were best at detecting land at shorter distances.

Results of the validation exercise suggest that effects of wave fetch on rocky shore communities are scale dependent. The greater effectiveness of summed wave fetch over a 2km radius than 100m scale data in predicting rocky shore community structure was not immediately anticipated, but was in line with previous results (Burrows et al., 2008) that showed 100m scale data to explain a smaller proportion of variance than 200m scale wave fetch data (also included in this analysis). One possible reason may be the lack of inclusion of wave refraction, allowing waves to change direction and focus energy around headlands that may otherwise have lower summed wave fetch values.

Further improvements in predictive power of this data may come from adding data on inshore depth. Thomas (1986) found that including the slope of the shore increased the fit of his analyses of littoral zone heights. The negative influence of shore extent on tendency for communities to be dominated by exposed shore species in this study was analogous to the reinforcing effect of shore slope on wave exposure in Thomas's study (1986). Rock platforms also attenuate waves as they break, potentially leading to reduced wave action in back reef areas where species typically found in more sheltered areas can persist. Shores with greater extent and likely consequential habitat complexity do tend to have greater species richness (Wells et al., 2007). An interaction effect between shore extent and summed wave fetch was seen in our analysis and was most likely associated with greater species richness and habitat diversity on extensive shores in both contrasting wave exposure conditions.

More species tended to be recorded during surveys of more extensive shores (species richness vs shore extent, $r=0.29$).

Data availability

All map data tiles are available at https://figshare.com/articles/Wave_fetch_GIS_layers_for_Europe_at_100m_scale/8668127, and may be subject to modification. R code for generating map layers is available at <https://github.com/michaelburrows/> (to be updated).

Acknowledgements

This research was co-funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe project “Marine Protected Areas for Europe (MPA Europe)” (HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-12 - *Improved science based maritime spatial planning and identification of marine protected areas*), grant agreement no. 101059988, and UKRI grant number 10069750. Landmass map data is copyrighted by OpenStreetMap contributors and available from <https://www.openstreetmap.org>. Ordnance Survey OpenData VectorMap data contains public sector information licensed under the Open Government Licence v3.0. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect that of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- Assis, J., Araújo, M.B., Serrão, E.A., 2018. Projected climate changes threaten ancient refugia of kelp forests in the North Atlantic. *Global Change Biology* 24, e55–e66.
- Baardseth, E., 1970. A square-scanning, two-stage sampling method of estimating seaweed quantities. *Rep. Norw. Inst. Seaweed Res.* 33, 1–41.
- Ballantine, W.J., 1961. A biologically-defined exposure scale for the comparative description of rocky shores. *Field Studies* 1, 1–19.
- Bekkby, T., Moy, F.E., 2011. Developing spatial models of sugar kelp (*Saccharina latissima*) potential distribution under natural conditions and areas of its disappearance in Skagerrak. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 95, 477–483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2011.10.029>
- Bertelli, C.M., Bennett, W.G., Karunaratna, H., Reeve, D.E., Unsworth, R.K.F., Bull, J.C., 2023. High-resolution wave data for improving marine habitat suitability models. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1004829>
- Burnham, K.P., Anderson, D.R., 2002. *Model Selection and Multimodel Inference: A Practical Information Theoretic Approach*. Springer Verlag, New York, USA.
- Burrows, M.T., 2012. Influences of wave fetch, tidal flow and ocean colour on subtidal rocky communities. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 445, 193–207. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps09422>
- Burrows, M.T., Fox, C.J., Moore, P., Smale, D., Sotheran, I., Benson, A., Greenhill, L., Martino, S., Parker, A., Thompson, E., Allen, C.J., 2018. Wild seaweed harvesting as a diversification opportunity for fishermen, A report by SRSI for HIE. Scottish Association for Marine Science, Oban, UK.
- Burrows, M.T., Harvey, R., Robb, L., 2008. Wave exposure indices from digital coastlines and the prediction of rocky shore community structure. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 353, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07284>
- Burrows, M.T., Hughes, R.N., 1989. Natural foraging of the dogwhelk, *Nucella lapillus* (Linnaeus): the weather and whether to feed. *Journal of Molluscan Studies* 55, 285–295.

- Chollett, I., Mumby, P.J., 2012. Predicting the distribution of *Montastraea* reefs using wave exposure. *Coral Reefs* 31, 493–503. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00338-011-0867-7>
- Crothers, J.H., 1983. Variation in dogwhelk shells in relation to wave action and crab predation. *Biol J Linn Soc* 20, 85–102.
- Davies, A.J., Johnson, M.P., Maggs, C.A., 2007. Limpet grazing and loss of *Ascophyllum nodosum* canopies on decadal time scales. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 339, 131–141.
- Eddelbuettel, D., Balamuta, J.J., 2018. Extending R with C++: A Brief Introduction to Repp. *The American Statistician* 72, 28–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2017.1375990>
- Ekebom, J., Laihonon, P., Suominen, T., 2003. A GIS-based step-wise procedure for assessing physical exposure in fragmented archipelagos. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 57, 887–898. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7714\(02\)00419-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7714(02)00419-5)
- Fitton, J.M., Hansom, J.D., Rennie, A.F., 2016. A national coastal erosion susceptibility model for Scotland. *Ocean & Coastal Management* 132, 80–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2016.08.018>
- García Molinos, J., Halpern, B.S., Schoeman, D.S., Brown, C.J., Kiessling, W., Moore, P.J., Pandolfi, J.M., Poloczanska, E.S., Richardson, A.J., Burrows, M.T., 2016. Climate velocity and the future global redistribution of marine biodiversity. *Nature Clim. Change* 6, 83–88. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2769>
- Gilbertson, N.M., Adams, T.P., Burrows, M.T., 2020. From marshes to coastlines: A metric for local and national scale identification of high-value habitat for coastal protection. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 107022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2020.107022>
- Harborne, A.R., Mumby, P.J., Zychaluk, K., Hedley, J.D., Blackwell, P.G., 2006. Modeling the beta diversity of coral reefs. *Ecology* 87, 2871–2881.
- Hijmans, R.J., 2022. raster: Geographic Data Analysis and Modeling.
- Isaeus, M., 2004. Factors structuring *Fucus* communities at open and complex coastlines in the Baltic Sea (PhD). Stockholm University, Stockholm.
- Lewis, J.R., 1964. *The Ecology of Rocky Shores*. English Universities Press London.
- Menge, B.A., 1978. Predation Intensity in a Rocky Intertidal Community. Effect of an Algal Canopy, Wave Action and Desiccation on Predator Feeding Rates. *Oecologia* 34, 17–35.
- Page, C., 1988. The Chromosome Complement of *Nucella Lapillus* (L.), Mollusca: Gastropoda: Prosobranchia. *Caryologia* 41, 79–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00087114.1988.10797850>
- Pascoe, P.L., 2006. Chromosomal polymorphism in the Atlantic dog-whelk, *Nucella lapillus* (Gastropoda: Muricidae): nomenclature, variation and biogeography. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 87, 195–210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.2006.00567.x>
- Pessarrodona, A., Assis, J., Filbee-Dexter, K., Burrows, M.T., Gattuso, J.-P., Duarte, C.M., Krause-Jensen, D., Moore, P.J., Smale, D.A., Wernberg, T., 2022. Global seaweed productivity. *Science Advances* 8, eabn2465. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abn2465>
- R Core Team, 2022. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- Ricketts, E., Calvin, J., 1992. *Between Pacific tides*. Stanford University Press.
- Ruuskanen, A., Bäck, S., Reitalu, T., 1999. A comparison of two cartographic exposure methods using *Fucus vesiculosus* as an indicator. *Marine Biology* 134, 139–145.
- Thomas, M.L.H., 1986. A physically derived exposure index for marine shorelines. *Ophelia* 25, 1–13.
- Wells, E., Wilkinson, M., Wood, P., Scanlan, C., 2007. The use of macroalgal species richness and composition on intertidal rocky seashores in the assessment of ecological quality under the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 151–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2006.08.031>
- Yesson, C., Bush, L.E., Davies, A.J., Maggs, C.A., Brodie, J., 2015. The distribution and environmental requirements of large brown seaweeds in the British Isles. *Journal of the*

Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom 95, 669–680.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315414001453>

Tables

Table 1. Linear models of community composition versus wave fetch. Terms included in the models were: wx32, 3x3 average 200m scale data from Burrows et al 2012; wx32100m, 3 x3 average 100m scale data this study; wf21, 21 x 21 average (2km) data from this study), shore extent (ShoreAreLT), and average August sea surface temperature (augsst). Fetch orientation was included in the last two of these models as cosine (wo32100mcos, East-West) and sine components (wo32100msin, North-South). Other abbreviations: adj.r squared, adjusted R-squared; AIC, Akaike's Information Criterion; dAIC, difference between the model AIC and the least AIC of the models compared. The * symbol between predictors indicates including interaction terms. All models were fitted to the same set of 238 PC1 values from intertidal surveys in Scotland in 2014-2015 and 2020-2022.

	Terms	r squared	adj.r squared	AIC	dAIC
A	pc1 ~ wx32	0.326	0.323	1146.6	51.5
B	pc1 ~ wx32 + ShoreAreLT + augsst	0.464	0.458	1095.0	0.0
C	pc1 ~ wx32 * ShoreAreLT + augsst	0.468	0.459	1095.6	0.6
D	pc1 ~ wx32100mlog10	0.234	0.231	1177.6	82.6
E	pc1 ~ wx32100mlog10 + ShoreAreLT + augsst	0.379	0.372	1130.7	35.7
F	pc1 ~ wx32100mlog10 + wf21log10 + ShoreAreLT + augsst	0.443	0.434	1106.5	11.5
G	pc1 ~ wx32100mlog10 * ShoreAreLT + wf21log10 + augsst	0.454	0.442	1103.7	8.7
H	pc1 ~ wf21log10 + ShoreAreLT + augsst	0.440	0.433	1105.8	10.8
I	pc1 ~ wf21log10 * ShoreAreLT + augsst	0.460	0.451	1099.0	4.0
J	pc1 ~ wx32100mlog10 + wo32100mcos + wo32100msin + ShoreAreLT + augsst	0.402	0.390	1125.5	30.5
K	pc1 ~ wx32100mlog10 * wo32100mcos * wo32100msin + ShoreAreLT + augsst	0.430	0.408	1122.2	27.2

Table 2. Model parameter coefficients from the two best performing models in Table 1. See Table 1 for details on the abbreviations

Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	
Model B					
(Intercept)	3.471	3.728	0.931	0.353	
wx32	3.738	0.2708	13.8	< 2e-16	***
ShoreAreLT	-0.000144	2.479E-05	-5.795	2.15E-08	***
augsst	-1.075	0.2685	-4.004	8.33E-05	***
Model I					
(Intercept)	-18.73	4.846	-3.864	0.000144	***
wf21log10	8.013	0.8131	9.856	< 2e-16	***
ShoreAreLT	0.000828	0.0003281	2.523	0.012292	*
augsst	-0.8243	0.2699	-3.054	0.002518	**
wf21log10:ShoreAreLT	-0.00024	8.103E-05	-2.957	0.003416	**

Figures

Figure 1. Regular 3-zone search patterns: (a,b) using fixed interval patterns (a) distant and middle-zone search, (b) middle and local search zones; and with random jitter (c, distant; d, middle and local zones), (e) frequency distribution of angles to the nearest land cell, (f) frequency distribution of distance to the nearest land.

Figure 2. Random search patterns using (a, b) squared random distance: (a) distant and middle-zone search, (b) local search; and (c, d) random log10 distance (c) distant and middle zone, (d) local search.

Figure 3. Frequency distribution of land check locations using three different search patterns.

(a) (b)
 (c) (d)
 Figure 4. Regular 3-zone search (a) without jitter; (b) with jitter ($n=2132$ checks per cell). Random search ($n=2000$ checks per cell) using random angles and (c) random \log_{10} distance, and (d) random square root maximum distance.

(c) (d)
 Figure 5. Differences of summed wave fetch values from model ensemble means for each land search pattern applied to the common test tiles shown in Figure 4. Lines show loess fits.

Figure 6. Example maps of the Bodø region in Norway showing (a) summed wave fetch, (b) fetch orientation (red, North; blue, South; green, East; yellow, West), and (c) standard deviation (SD) of fetch orientation. Wave fetch metrics produced using the regular 3-zone search pattern with jitter.

(a) (b)
 Figure 7. Community composition versus wave fetch: exposure-affinity species PC1 scores for rocky shore communities in Scotland (2014-2015 and 2020-2022) against summed wave fetch (log₁₀ summed distance in 100-m grid cell units) averaged over (a) 3 x 3 cell neighbourhoods, and (b) 21 x 21 cell (2km) neighbourhoods. Positive values for PC1 denote greater dominance by wave-exposure affinity species. Red circles show data from 2014-2015 and black circles 2020-2022.

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Figure 1. PCA factor loadings. Abbreviations *Acequ*, *Actinia equina*; *Acfra*, *Actinia fragacea*; *Alesc*, *Alaria esculenta*; *Anvir*, *Anemonia viridis*; *Asnod*, *Ascophyllum nodosum*; *Asrub*, *Asterias rubens*; *Auver*, *Aulactinia verrucosa*; *Bacre*, *Balanus crenatus*; *Baper*, *Balanus perforatus*; *Bibif*, *Bifurcaria bifurcata*; *Caziz*, *Calliostoma zizphinum*; *Cheri*, *Chondrus crispus*; *Chmon*, *Chthamalus montagui*; *Chste*, *Chthamalus stellatus*; *Clery*, *Clibanarius erythropus*; *Cooff*, *Corallina officinalis*; *Cosp*, *Codium sp*; *Elmod*, *Austrominius modestus*; *Fudis*, *Fucus distichus*; *Fuser*, *Fucus serratus*; *Fuspi*, *Fucus spiralis*; *Fuves*, *Fucus vesiculosus*; *Gicin*, *Steromphala cineraria*; *Gipen*, *Steromphala pennanti*; *Giumb*, *Steromphala umbilicalis*; *Hapan*, *Halichondria panicea*; *Hasil*, *Halidrys siliquosa*; *Hatub*, *Haliotis tuberculata*; *Hielo*, *Himanthalia elongata*; *Ladig*, *Laminaria digitata*; *Lahyp*, *Laminaria hyperborea*; *Laoch*, *Laminaria ochroleuca*; *Lemue*, *Leptasterias muelleri*; *Lilit*, *Littorina littorea*; *Lipyg*, *Lichina pygmaea*; *Lisax*, *Littorina saxatilis*; *Maste*, *Mastocarpus stellatus*; *Mener*, *Melarhapha neritoides*; *Myspp*, *Mytilus edulis*; *Nulap*, *Nucella lapillus*; *Oncel*, *Onchidella celtica*; *Oslin*, *Phorcus lineatus*; *Padep*, *Patella depressa*; *Paliv*, *Paracentrotus lividus*; *Papal*, *Palmaria palmata*; *Pauly*, *Patella ulyssiponensis*; *Pavul*, *Patella vulgata*; *Pecan*, *Pelvetia canaliculata*; *Saalv*, *Sabellaria alveolata*; *Samut*, *Sargassum muticum*; *Sapol*, *Saccorhiza polyschides*; *Sebal*, *Semibalanus balanoides*; *Stdro*, *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*; *Tetes*, *Testudinalia testudinalis*;

Supplementary Figure 2. Fetch orientation and August sea surface temperatures for rocky shore survey sites.

